

Synthesis of 1,2,4-Triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one Nucleosides and their Antileishmanial Activity

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6-β-D-Ribofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (5), 6-β-D-xylofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (7), 6-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (9) and 6-[(1,3-dihydroxy-2-propoxy)methyl]-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (11) have been synthesised. Compounds 2, 5, 7, 9 and 11 showed 70, 40, 65, 0 and 78% inhibition of the growth of amastigotes of *Leishmania donovani* in hamster at 25 mg/kg dose.

In recent years the naturally occurring purine and pyrimidine nucleosides and nucleotides and their synthetic analogues have attracted considerable attention because some of the nucleosides exhibit a wide variety of specific biological activity¹⁻⁶. The activities of these nucleosides is largely due to the structural similarity to the natural enzyme substrates. These analogues either emulate or antagonise the function of naturally occurring purine and pyrimidine nucleosides.

Purine and pyrimidine bases in the biological system are ribosylated and the corresponding ribosides are selectively phosphorylated at 5'-position in the sugar moiety. It is the 5'-triphosphate of the nucleosides which is the active species. There are reports where the ribosides are found more effective than the bases⁷. Whereas, nucleotides due to their ionic character pose problem of transport across the cell membrane.

The interesting biological properties of 1-β-D-arabinofuranosylcytosine (ara-C)⁸⁻¹⁰, 9-β-D-arabinofuranosyladenine (ara-A)¹¹⁻¹⁴ and certain 5'-monophosphate of 9-β-D-arabinofuranosyladenine¹⁵ and 9-β-D-arabinofuranosylhypoxanthine¹⁶⁻¹⁸ have aroused considerable interest in nucleosides derived from β-D-arabinofuranose. The effectiveness of 2-amino-6-oxo-9-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)purine (acyclovir)⁹ effective against a number of viral infection, has aroused considerable interest in nonclassical nucleosides. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise classical and nonclassical nucleosides of 1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (2). This heterocyclic system is of particular interest since it provides additional binding sites in a pyrimidine skeleton. In the present communication, we report the synthesis of 6-β-D-ribofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (5), 6-β-D-xylofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (7), 6-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (9) and 6-[(1,3-dihydroxy-2-propoxy)methyl]-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (11) and their antileishmanial activity.

s-Triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (2)¹⁹ (Scheme 1) was prepared by cyclisation of 4-hydra-

zino-2-oxopyrimidine (1) with formic acid followed by Dimroth rearrangement. Treatment of 2 with hexamethyldisilazane in presence of ammonium

Scheme 1

zino-2-oxopyrimidine (1) with formic acid followed by Dimroth rearrangement. Treatment of 2 with hexamethyldisilazane in presence of ammonium sulphate according to the general procedure described by Wittenburg²⁰ gave the trimethylsilyl derivative 3 which without further purification was reacted with 2,3,5-tri-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-ribofuranose in the presence of SnCl₄ in 1,2-dichloroethane at ambient temperature. Under these conditions, 6-(2,3,5-tri-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-ribofuranosyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (4) was obtained in moderate yield. The nucleoside 4 was the only nucleoside which could be detected by tlc or

column chromatography. Similarly, in other glycosylation reactions reported in this study no other nucleosides were detected by tlc other than those isolated and characterised in the experimental part. Treatment of 4 with methanolic ammonia at ambient temperature finally afforded the deprotected nucleoside (5). The elemental analysis and other spectroscopic data of the nucleoside were in complete agreement with the assigned structure.

Although the anomeric configuration of 5 could tentatively be assigned as β on the basis of several empirical rules²¹, and by a large positive rotation²² ($[\alpha]_D^{20} + 47.7^\circ$) of the nucleoside 5. A more rigorous proof for the anomeric configuration emerged from its nmr spectral data. Pmr spectrum of 5 in Me₂SO-*d*₆ revealed a doublet (for C_{1'}H) centered at δ 6.0 with a $J_{1',2'}$ of approximately 4 Hz; thus confirming β -configuration²³.

The glycosylation site in 5 is established by using ¹³C nmr spectroscopy. Several nmr spectral studies have recently demonstrated the potential use of ¹³C nmr spectroscopy as a general unequivocal method for the assignment of glycosylation site in fused heteroaromatic compounds. It has been reported²⁴ that protonation of nitrogen results in an upfield shift for the carbon α to the protonated nitrogen while a down field shift is observed for the β -carbon. The ¹³C chemical shift of the anion of *s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5-one (2) as well as the nucleoside are summarised in Table 1. In the

has been synthesised earlier from cytidine in several steps²⁶. Our new synthesis of riboside 5 has been achieved in fewer steps.

Condensation of the trimethyl silyl derivative (3) with 1,2,3,5-*O*-acetyl-*D*-xylofuranose in presence of SnCl₄ in 1,2-dichloroethane at ambient temperature furnished 6-(2,3,4-tri-*O*-acetyl- β -*D*-xylofuranosyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (6) in 65% yield. Deblocking of 6 with methanolic ammonia at room temperature gave 6- β -*D*-xylofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (7). The β -configuration for the xyloside (7) is discerned from its pmr spectral data. The pmr spectrum of 7 had a doublet at δ 5.9 ($J_{1',2'}$, 3.5 Hz) for the anomeric proton H-1' of the xyloside. A large upfield shift of δ 13.5 ppm for C₇ and a small downfield shift of δ 1 ppm for C₈ confirmed that N₆ of the pyrimidine system is the site of glycosylation.

Condensation of *s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5-one (2) with benzoyloxyethoxymethyl chloride²⁷ in DMF using triethylamine as acid quencher gave the protected acyclic nucleoside (8). Deblocking of 8 with methanolic ammonia at ambient temperature yielded 6-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (6). A large upfield shift of δ 8.5 ppm for C₇ and a small downfield shift of δ 2 ppm for C₈ in the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the nucleoside was suggestive of N₆ of pyrimidine derivative (6), the site of glycosylation.

Condensation of *s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5-one (2) with 2-*O*-chloromethyl-1,3-di-*O*-benzylglycerol²⁸ in the presence of triethylamine gave the protected acyclic nucleoside (10). Hydrogenolysis of 10 with PdCl₂/H₂ finally afforded the acyclic nucleoside (11).

Antileishmanial activity: The compounds were evaluated for antileishmanial activity (*in vivo*) against amastigotes of *Leishmania donovani* in hamsters according to the procedure described earlier²⁹ and compounds 2, 5, 6, 9 and 10 exhibited 70, 40, 65, 0 and 78% inhibition respectively at 25 mg/kg on the 7th day. Allopurinol was used as a standard drug which showed 90% inhibition at 25 mg/kg. The data revealed that ribosylation and xylosylation of the heterocycle (2) did not increase the activity. Since 6- β -*D*-xylofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (6) was found more active (65% inhibition) than 6- β -*D*-ribofuranosyl-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (5) (inhibition 40%) at the same dose (25 mg/kg), the data suggest that the configuration of hydroxy function at position-3' in the sugar moiety influences the antileishmanial activity of the nucleosides. Further, 6-[(1,3-dihydroxy-2-propoxy)methyl]-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (10) was found most active (78% inhibition) at 25 mg/kg, suggesting that alicyclic nucleoside of *s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5-one (2) are more active than the classical riboside and xyloside. However, the alicyclic nucleoside, 6-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-*s*-triazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrimidin-5(6*H*)-one (9) was found inactive at 25 mg/kg dose. The data indicate that the chainlength and also disposition

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF ¹³C-CHEMICAL SHIFTS FOR *s*-TRIAZOLO[2,3-*c*]PYRIMIDINE ANION AND ITS NUCLEOSIDES

Compd. no.	Chemical shift (δ ppm)		
	C ₈	C ₇	C ₆
2 anion	151.5	147.5	95
5	154	134	96
7	156	135	96
9	156	139	97

pmr spectrum of 2, H-2 appeared as singlet at δ 8.52 whereas H-7 and H-8 appeared at δ 7.7 and 6.85 as doublets (J 8 Hz) respectively. In the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the compound the C₇ and C₈ carbons showed large ¹³C-¹H splittings caused by the directly attached protons. The C₈ signal in the base 2 is expected to occur considerably downfield followed by C₇ and C₆ due to deshielding effect of the adjacent nitrogen²⁵. In the ¹³C nmr spectrum of the anion 2 the signals at δ 151.5, 147.5 and 95 were thus assigned to C₈, C₇ and C₆ respectively. By comparing the chemical shifts of the anion of 2 and those of riboside 5, a large upfield shift of δ 12.5 ppm is observed for C₇ and a small downfield shift of δ 1 ppm is observed for C₈ suggesting that the pyrimidine N₆ is the site of ribosylation. The N₆ ribosylation is also corroborated by high positive rotation as pyrimidine- β -*D*-ribosides show similar sign of rotation²². The ribose 10 reported above

of hydroxyl functions in the glycone moiety are critical for antileishmanial activity in this series of nucleosides.

Experimental

Experimental details are to be found in our earlier paper in the series²⁷.

6-(2,3,5-Tri-O-benzoyl-β-D-ribofuranosyl)-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (4): A mixture of *s*-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (2) (1.0 g, 7.4 mmol), (NH₄)₂SO₄ (0.1 g) and trimethylsilyl chloride (TMS 2 ml) in freshly distilled hexamethyl-disilazane (HMDS, 10 ml) was refluxed for 26 h under anhydrous conditions. The excess of HMDS was then removed from the resulting mixture under reduced pressure. The resulting silyl derivative (3) was used for subsequent reaction without further purification.

1-O-Acetyl-2,3,5-tri-O-benzoyl-D-ribofuranose (5) (5.65 g, 11.2 mmol) in anhydrous dichloroethane (150 ml) was added to a solution of trimethylsilyl derivative (3) in dichloroethane (50 ml). To it was added tin(IV) chloride (2.3 ml, 8.9 mmol) and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at ambient temperature. The resulting mixture was poured into aqueous NaHCO₃ solution and filtered through celite. The organic layer was separated, washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ solution and H₂O, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (97:3, v/v) yielded 4 (1.3 g, 31%), m.p. 200-02° (Found: C, 62.6; H, 4.3; N, 9.3. C₂₁H₁₉N₄O₈·H₂O requires: C, 62.2; H, 4.0; N, 9.4%); δ (CDCl₃) 8.2 (1H, s, H-2), 8.0-7.8 (7H, m, H-7, PhH adjacent to C=O), 7.8-7.3 (9H, m, PhH), 6.8 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 6.5 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, H-1'), 6.1-5.8 (3H, m, H-2', H-3' and H-4') and 4.8-4.6 (2H, m, H-5').

6-β-D-Ribofuranosyl-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (5): A mixture of 4 (1.0 g, 1.7 mmol) and methanolic NH₃ (50 ml, MeOH at 0° saturated with NH₃) was kept at ambient temperature for 48 h. Methanol and the excess of NH₃ were then removed under reduced pressure. The product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (82:18, v/v) gave 5 (0.24 g, 52%), m.p. 183-84° (abs. MeOH) (lit.²⁰ 182-85°) (Found: C, 44.3; H, 4.6; N, 20.5. C₁₀H₁₂N₄O₆ requires: C, 44.7; H, 4.5; N, 20.9%); [α]_D²⁰ = +47.7 (c, 1% DMSO); pmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.4 (1H, s, H-2), 8.1 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 6.9 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 6.0 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, H-1'), 5.5 (1H, m, H-2'), 5.23 (1H, m, H-3'), 5.14 (1H, m, H-4'), 3.6 (2H, m, H-5'); cmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 154 (C-2), 134 (C-7), 96 (C-8), 90 (C-1'), 84 (C-4'), 74 (C-2'), 69 (C-3') and 60 (C-5').

6-(2,3,5-Tri-O-acetyl-β-D-xylofuranosyl)-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (6): A mixture of 3 (1.5 g, 11.0 mmol), 1,2,3,5-tetra-O-acetyl-D-xylofuranose (6.5 g, 20 mmol), dichloroethane (100 ml)

and SnCl₄ (5.2 ml, 20 mmol) was stirred for 24 h at ambient temperature. The resulting mixture was poured into saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution and filtered through celite. The organic layer was separated, washed with H₂O, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The crude product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on a SiO₂ column. Elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (9:2, v/v) yielded 6 as foam (2.8 g, 65%) m/z 394 (M⁺); pmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.2 (1H, s, H-2), 7.6 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 6.73 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 6.23 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz, H-1'), 5.35 (1H, m, H-2'), 5.23 (1H, m, H-3'), 4.55 (1H, m, H-4') 4.35 (2H, m, H-5'), 2.1, 2.08 and 2.05 (9H, each s, COCH₃).

6-β-D-Xylofuranosyl-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (7): A mixture of 6 (2.5 g, 6.3 mmol) and methanolic NH₃ (100 ml, MeOH at 0° saturated with NH₃) was kept at ambient temperature for 48 h. The excess NH₃ and the solvent were removed. The product thus obtained, was crystallised from absolute MeOH to yield 7 (1.2 g, 70%), m.p. 205-06° (Found: C, 43.8; H, 4.6; N, 19.8. C₁₀H₁₂N₄O₆·0.5 H₂O requires: C, 43.3; H, 4.7; N, 20.2%); [α]_D²⁰ = +12.6 (c, 1% DMSO); m/z 268 (M⁺); pmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.4 (1H, s, H-2), 7.95 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 6.85 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 5.9 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz, H-1'), 4.4-3.9 (3H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4') and 3.9-3.6 (2H, m, H-5'); cmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 156 (C-2), 135 (C-7), 96 (C-8), 93 (C-1'), 85.5 (C-4'), 81.5 (C-2'), 75.4 (C-3') and 60 (C-5').

6-(2-Benzoyloxyethoxymethyl)-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (8): To a mixture of 2 (1.0 g, 7.3 mmol), DMF (50 ml) and Et₃N (5 ml) was added dropwise a solution of 2-benzoyloxyethoxymethyl chloride²⁷ (4.0 g, 18 mmol) in dry DMF (20 ml) and the reaction mixture stirred for 18 h. The excess Et₃N and the solvent were removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was extracted with EtOAc, washed with H₂O, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution with EtOAc-MeOH (90:10, v/v) afforded 8 as an oil (0.6 g, 60%); pmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.3 (1H, s, H-2), 8.2-7.3 (6H, m, H-7 and PhH), 6.75 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 5.55 (2H, s, H-1'), 4.6-4.3 (2H, m, H-3') and 4.3-3.8 (2H, m, H-4').

6-(2-Hydroxyethoxymethyl)-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (9): A mixture of 8 (1.5 g, 4.7 mmol) and methanolic NH₃ (50 ml, MeOH at 0° saturated with NH₃) was kept at ambient temperature for 24 h. The excess NH₃ and the solvent were removed from the resulting mixture. The product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution of the column with EtOAc-MeOH (85:15, v/v) afforded 9, m.p. 150-53° (EtOH) (Found: C, 45.5; H, 4.8; N, 26.5. C₈H₁₀N₄O₆ requires: C, 45.7; H, 4.8; N, 26.7%); m/z 210 (M⁺); pmr δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) 8.2 (1H, s, H-2), 7.65 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 6.75 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 5.5 (2H, s, H-1') and 3.7 (4H, bs, H-3' and H-4'); cmr δ (DMSO-d₆) 156 (C-2),

139 (C-7), 97 (C-8), 79.5 (C-1'), 72 (C-3') and 61 (C-4').

6-[[1,3-Bis(benzyloxy-2-propoxy)methyl]-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidine-5,6H)-one (10): A mixture of 2 (1.0 g, 7.3 mmol), dry DMF (50 ml) and Et₃N (5 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature. To it was added a solution of 2-chloromethyl-1,3-dibenzylpropanol²⁰ (4.0 g) in dry DMF (20 ml) and stirring continued for 24 h. The excess Et₃N and the solvent were removed under reduced pressure. The resulting crude product was extracted with EtOAc, washed with H₂O, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The product, thus obtained, was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution with CHCl₃-MeOH (85 : 15, v/v) afforded 10 as an oil (0.56 g, 56%); pmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.1 (1H, s, H-2), 7.35 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 7.15 (10H, s, PhH), 6.4 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 5.45 (2H, s, N-CH₂-O), 4.3 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂Ph), 3.8-4.1 (1H, m, H-3') and 3.6-3.4 (4H, m, CH(CH₂O)₂).

6-[[1,3-Dihydroxy-2-propoxy)methyl]-s-triazolo[2,3-c]pyrimidin-5(6H)-one (11): A mixture of 10 (1.5 g, 5.2 mmol) and PdCl₂ (0.05 g) in MeOH (100 ml) was shaken in H₂ atmosphere (40 lb pressure) for 12 h and filtered. The filtrate was passed through ion-exchange resin (IR-45, OH-form) and eluted with MeOH. The solvent from the elute was removed, and the resulting product was chromatographed on SiO₂ column. Elution with CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10, v/v) afforded 11 (0.8 g, 53%), m.p. 130-32° (EtOH) (Found: C, 42.1; H, 5.2; N, 21.2. C₉H₁₃N₄O₄·H₂O requires C, 41.8; H, 5.5; N, 21.7%); m/z 240 (M⁺); pmr δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) 8.3 (1H, s, H-2), 7.9 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-7), 6.85 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-8), 5.72 (2H, s, H-1'), 4.6-4.2 (1H, m, H-3') and 3.9-3.4 (4H, m, H-4' and H-5').

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